

IMPORTANCE OF WOMEN'S EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article gives information about the importance of women's education. A well-educated woman provides the skills, knowledge, and self-assurance necessary to be a better mom, worker, and citizen. A well-educated woman will also be more productive and well-paid at work. Indeed, the return on investment in education is often higher for women than for males.

Key words: educated women, female education, investment, priority

There was a period when it was considered that women didn't need to be educated. We've now realized the importance of women's education. The modern era is the phase of women's awakening. In every aspect of life, women are striving to compete with males. Many individuals reject female education, claiming that women's rightful domain is the home, and therefore that money spent on female education is squandered. This viewpoint is incorrect since female education has the potential to bring about a silent revolution in society.

Female education has numerous advantages; educated women may contribute significantly to the country's growth by sharing the burdens of males in several fields. They may contribute to society as teachers, lawyers, physicians, and administrators, as well as play a key part in wartime. In this time of economic distress, education is a blessing for women. The days of wealth and prosperity are long gone. Middle-class families are finding it increasingly difficult to make ends meet these days. Female education is important for a country's growth, thus it should be supported. Everyone has hope for a better life if they have an education. It's a type of magic that works in a person's life to make it far better than it would be if he didn't have knowledge. We believe that everyone should be educated so that they can contribute to making our country proud. Increasing literacy rates can prevent tens of thousands of crimes. Every country should encourage its citizens to receive an education.

Girls have the right same right to education as boys. Educated girls can make informed choices – and from a far better range of options. Educating girls saves lives and builds stronger families, communities and economies.

An educated female population increases a country's productivity and fuels economic growth. Some countries lose more than \$1 billion a year by failing to educate girls to the same level as boys. Despite this, girls and young women in many parts of the world miss out on school every day. Around 61 million girls are of school, according to UNICEF in 2016 – 32 million girls of primary school age and 29 million of lower secondary school age. Often, girls are marginalised and are out of school simply because they are girls and it is not the cultural norm. Their chances of getting a quality education are even smaller if they come from a poor family, live in a rural area or have a disability. Girls are four times more likely to be out of school than boys from the same background. The poorest girls also have the least likelihood of completing primary school. There are often legal, religious and traditional practices that discriminate against girls having the chance to get an education. Ensuring that all girls and young women receive a quality education is their human right, a global development priority, and a strategic priority for the World Bank. Achieving gender equality is central to the World Bank Group

twin goals of ending extreme poverty and boosting shared prosperity. As the largest financing development partner in education globally, the World Bank ensures that all of its education projects are gender-sensitive, and works to overcome barriers that are preventing girls and boys from equally benefiting from countries' investments in education.

Girls' education goes beyond getting girls into school. It is also about ensuring that girls learn and feel safe while in school; have the opportunity to complete all levels of education, acquiring the knowledge and skills to compete in the labor market; gain socio-emotional and life skills necessary to navigate and adapt to a changing world; make decisions about their own lives; and contribute to their communities and the world. Both individuals and countries benefit from girls' education. Better educated women tend to be more informed about nutrition and healthcare, have fewer children, marry at a later age, and their children are usually healthier, should they choose to become mothers. They are more likely to participate in the formal labor market and earn higher incomes. Education Women have now taken places in all our formal institutions of learning. Educated women have organised enlightenment programmes to enlighten Nigerian women on their roles in national development. Also workshops, seminars and conferences are organized to educate women on the means and ways of acquiring political and economic power. Adult Education classes are established in the rural areas. There have been successful and innovative programmes such as using local extension agents in rural areas or establishing flexible educational initiatives that fit with women's schedules. Other projects include day-care centres for women who otherwise could not have attended courses.

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